

Undercuts: A Critical Factor Affecting the Integrity and Reliability of Structures with Butt-Welded Joints

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ABSTRACT

Steel structures in the European Union are typically designed according to EN 1993. The execution, in turn, follows the guidelines of EN 1090-2. When evaluating welded joints, especially with regard to weld imperfections, EN 1090-2 refers to EN ISO 5817. In recent years, notable inconsistencies have been identified between the design and execution standards.

The assessment of weld imperfections in EN ISO 5817 relies on quality levels with hard boundaries. However, there is a valid question about whether the boundaries for weld imperfections, as defined by the quality level limits, truly represent a realistic threshold for load-bearing capacity. This is crucial because there is a lack of experimental data linking the size of weld imperfections to the load-bearing capacity of welded joints and the standard was originally developed to enhance communication between welders and inspectors.

Weld imperfections, such as undercuts, can significantly impact the strength and integrity of welded structures. This study investigates the influence of undercuts on the load-bearing capacity of butt-welded joints. Ten test specimens were fabricated with different undercut depths and subjected to tensile tests at room temperature and -30°C.

The results demonstrate that undercuts can have a substantial impact on the load-bearing capacity of a weld joint, with deeper undercuts leading to lower failure strains and load-bearing capacities. However, some joints with undercuts did not fail in the undercut itself, but instead in the sheet metal. This suggests that the overall quality of the weld joint, in addition to the severity of undercuts, plays a crucial role in determining its load-bearing capacity.

Keywords: Weld imperfection, butt-welded joints, undercuts,

1 INTRODUCTION

The history of welding in structural steel is a story of technological evolution, transforming construction practices over the centuries. While ancient blacksmiths employed basic methods to join metals, the pivotal breakthrough came in the late 19th century with the advent of arc welding.

The 20th century witnessed the widespread adoption of welding in structural steel construction, replacing traditional methods like riveting. World War II accelerated advancements, necessitating rapid and efficient construction of military infrastructure. Post WWII the development of welding codes and standards gained momentum. These codes aimed to provide clear criteria for evaluating the quality of welds. Codes, such as the AWS D1 series (1) in the United States and DIN 8560 in Germany, began to include specific requirements for different types of welded joints. The establishment of international standards, such as ISO 3834 and EN ISO 5817 (2), further harmonized quality requirements for welds on a global scale. These standards address aspects like welding procedure qualification, personnel qualification, and quality levels for imperfections in welded structures.

Nowadays, welding is nearly used in every steel structure and there is an extremely large number of national and international standards regulating welding and related topics. In general Steel structures

in the European Union have to be designed acc. to EN 1993 (3) and executed acc. to EN 1090-2 (4). For the assessment of welded seams, the EN 1090-2 (4) refers to EN ISO 5817 (2). However, despite all the evolution in technology and international standardisation even up-to-date there is a lag of research considering the correlation between weld quality levels and imperfections size postulated in EN ISO 5817 (2). In this article the influence of undercuts on the load-bearing capacity of butt-welded joints will be investigated.

2 CURRENT REGULATION IN STANDARDS

Most common weld imperfections are listed and described in EN ISO 6520-1 (5). Regarding undercuts the standard divides between continuous and intermittent undercuts, where continuous undercuts are those “of significant length without interruption” and intermittent undercuts are “short length of undercut, intermittent along the weld”. In EN ISO 6520-1 (5) there are also inter-run undercuts which are located in longitudinal direction between weld runs and shrinkage grooves, undercuts on each side of the root run. EN ISO 5817 (2) only divides between continuous, intermittent undercuts and shrinkage groove. The characteristic size of the imperfection is the depth of the undercuts and the allowed limits are linked to the sheet thickness (see Table 1).

Table 1: EN ISO 5817 (2)

No.	Reference to ISO 6520-1	Imperfection designation	Remarks	t [mm]	Limits for imperfections for quality levels		
					D	C	B
1.7	5011	continuous undercuts	Smooth transition is required. This is not regarded as a systematic imperfection.	0.5 to 3	Short imperfection: $h \leq 0.2 t$	Short imperfection: $h \leq 0.1 t$	Not permitted
	5012	intermittent undercuts		> 3	$h \leq 0.2 t$, but max. 1 mm	$h \leq 0.1 t$, but max. 0.5 mm	$h \leq 0.05 t$, but max. 0.5 mm
1.8	5013	Shrinkage groove	Smooth transition is required.	0.5 to 3	Short imperfection: $h \leq 0.2 t + 0.1 t$	Short imperfection: $h \leq 0.1 t$	Not permitted
				> 3	$h \leq 0.2 t$, but max. 2 mm	$h \leq 0.1 t$, but max. 1 mm	$h \leq 0.05 t$, but max. 0.5 mm

Considering the quality level limits for a sheet thickness higher than 3 mm there is no difference between continuous and intermittent undercuts. The relative limits are with 5 %, 10 % and 20 % of the sheet thickness quite big. However, there are absolute limits as well limiting the undercut depth to 1 mm for quality level D and 0.5 mm for quality level C and B. As a result, the absolute limit for quality level D and C is reached for sheets 5 mm thick on the one hand and on the other hand, not until 10 mm sheet thickness for quality level B.

Comparing acceptable limits of undercuts and shrinkage groove relative limits are the same for quality level D to B. Nevertheless, absolute limits for level D and C are twice the size of those for undercuts.

The quality levels are directly connected to the execution classes (EXC) of EN 1090-2 (4). EXC1 has the lowest requirements for steel structures and only requires quality level D while EXC2 requires quality level C and consequently quality level B is required for EXC3. Additionally all joints designed according to EN 1993-1-8 (6) require EXC2 and therefore at least quality level C of EN ISO 5817 (2).

In VOLVO STD 181-0004 (7) undercut depth is limited to 20 % of the sheet thickness and should not be greater than 2 mm. The latest version of AWS D1.1 (8) allows undercuts until a depth of 2 mm for material less than 25 mm thick. Where the accumulated length of the undercut should not exceed

50 mm in any 300 mm. The limits for material equal or greater than 25 mm are the same but length is not limited.

Fig. 1. Characteristic geometric parameters of undercuts

As depicted in Fig. 1 is the shape of the undercut typically described by the following four parameters:

- Undercut depth (h): The vertical distance from the root of the weld to the surface of the base metal.
- Undercut width (b): The horizontal distance from the edge of the undercut to the edge of the weld face.
- Undercut radius (r): The Radius at the bottom of the undercut
- Undercut opening angle (β): The angle between the two sides of the undercut.

However, if the undercuts depth is small compared to the radius the shape can also be described without the opening angle β .

In a general, undercuts can be described as rounded when they are flat and wide or as sharp when they are narrow and or deep. The undercut depth h is the most important parameter in terms of the strength of the weld joint, as it directly reduces the cross-sectional area of the weld. The undercut width, angle and radius also affect the strength of the welded joint, as they can affect the stress concentrations at the undercut.

3 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

3.1 Experimental program

In order to investigate the influence of undercuts on the load-bearing capacity, experimental tests were carried out on special test specimens. For the experimental investigations, undercuts were intentionally introduced into the welded joint. The experimental study was conducted on ten specimens. All specimens were butt-welded joints with a gauge area of 200 mm times 20 mm. The gauge length was 700 mm. The dimensions of the specimens are depicted in Fig. 2 together with the boundary conditions. During the tests the specimens were clamped at both ends while the displacement was applied on the left end. All tests were carried out displacement controlled with a speed of 1 mm/min. Seven specimens were tested at room temperature while three specimens were tested at $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ which is the lowest operation temperature in Germany according to (9). For the low temperature tests the specimens were boxed in a climber chamber over the gauge length and nitrogen was introduced via plates with were clammed to the specimen at both ends of the gauge length.

Fig. 2. Specimen dimensions and boundary conditions

All joints had the same preparation before welding which is depicted in Fig. 3 a). The pass sequence was also the same for all ten test specimens and is depicted in Fig. 3 b). Before the back side was welded the root has been grounded out, to ensure good fusion and penetration of the weld. The welding details are listed in Table 2. The welding process used has been Gas Metal Arc Welding (GMAW) and all passes have been carried out in a flat position (PA). As filler material EN ISO 14341(10)-A: G 2Si and as shielding gas M21 has been used. The base material is S355J2+N.

Fig. 3. a) Joint preparation (Dimensions in mm) b) Pass sequences

During the investigations the displacement of the piston and the force were measured. In addition, displacement transducers over a length of 400 mm and strain gauges have been arranged in the gauge area.

Table 2. Welding details

Pass	Intensity [A]	Arc voltage [V]	Wire feed Speed [m/min]	Travel Speed [cm/min]	Welding Energy [kJ/cm]
1	100	17	3.5	14.1	5.79
2-4	220	28.2	11.1	12	24.82
5-6	220	28.2	11.1	10	29.78
7	220	28.2	11.1	15	19.85

3.2 Geometrical properties

One way to inspect weld joints for defects is to use 3D scanning. With 3D scanning a digital representation of the weld joint can be created, which can then be used to measure the geometric dimensions of the weld and the defects. Before testing the specimens until failure 3D-scans were carried for the weld region of every specimen. Later on, all characteristic geometric have been measured using GOM Correlate.

For manufacturing widths and depths were specified for the notch in order to produce both sharp and rounded notches. The planned value as well as the actual values for both width and depth are depicted

in Fig. 4 a) and b). Considering a given sheet thickness of 20 mm the quality level limits of EN ISO 5817 (2) are 1 mm for quality level D and 0.5 mm for quality level C and quality level B with are also depicted in Fig. 4 a).

As depicted, all specimens, except specimen A0, have undercuts above the limits of quality level B and C and should therefore not be tolerated for joints designed according to EN ISO 1993-1-8 (6). Specimen A0 was planned with no undercut and is used as a reference specimen. Considering undercut depth presented in Fig. 4 a) the specimens can be separated into three groups. One with undercut depth of around 1 mm (A1, A4, A7), the other with an undercut depth of 2 mm (A2, A5, A8) and the third one with an undercut depth of around 4.5 mm (A3, A6, A9).

Bearing in mind the width of the undercuts depicted in Fig. 4 b) the specimens cannot be clearly grouped. However, undercut width is measured at the top of the undercut so to proper describe the shape the opening angle of the undercut (see Fig. 4 c) and the radius at the ground of the undercut (see Fig. 4 d) also have to be considered. All in all, specimen A1 to A6 and A9 have a radius of around 1 mm and are therefore rather sharp while specimen A7 and A8 could be described as rounded.

Fig. 4. Characteristic geometry size of all undercuts a) undercut depth b) undercut width c) undercut opening angle d) undercut radius

3.3 Material properties

In Fig. 5 depicts macrosections of specimen A4 (a) and A8 (b). Both show a clear separation the base material and the weld with a clear visible head affected zone. All welds have a V-shape while the narrows part of the weld is at the root.

Fig. 5. Macrosection a) specimen A4 b) specimen A8

The base material has a yield strength of 327 MPa and is below the known values of S355. However, tensile strength of 522 MPa, uniform elongation of 16 % and fracture strain of 34 % are within the normal range (see also Fig. 6 a).

Comparing the properties of the base material to the weld material, the yield strength of weld material is much higher than those of the base material and with 436 MPa in normal range for G2Si1. Nevertheless, the tensile strength of the base material is with 526 MPa only slightly higher. Uniform elongation (11 %) and fracture strain (23 %) are smaller compared to the values of the base material. The stress-strain curve of the weld material is depicted in Fig. 6 b).

Fig. 6. Stress-strain curve a) base material b) filler material

Additional to the tensile tests Charpy tests were conducted for both, base material and weld material at room temperature and at -30 °C. Example force-displacement curves for one Charpy test at room temperature and -30 °C are depicted in Fig. 7 for a) the base material and b) the weld material. In average the impact energy for the base material is 163 J at 23 °C and 66 J at -30 °C. The average impact energy of the weld material is lower at room temperature (144 J) and higher at -30 °C (80 J) as the average impact energy of the base material. Regarding the impact energy both material fulfil the requirements of (10) and (11).

Fig. 7. Force-displacement curves of Charpy tests a) base material b) filler material

3.4 Test results

The results of the large-scale tests are depicted in Fig. 8 for the tests at $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in (a) and at room temperature (b) using force-strain curves with the strain calculated over a length 400 mm. In both figures the blue line represents specimen A0 with is considered as a joint without defects and should serve as a reference. Considering the different test temperatures lower testing temperature leads to a higher strength in the material as depicted in Fig. 8 a). Though, the offset is in normal range according to (12). Despite that, Fig. 8 a) shows a reduction of the strain at failure with growing undercut depth even though the force-strain curves look quite similar for lower strains. For a small undercut (specimen A1) no reduction in maximum force or strain is visible.

A comparable visual representation is provided in Fig. 8 b). As well as at low temperatures, with growing undercut depth failure strain gets reduced. Although, specimen A4 reaches a similar maximum force and has a higher failure strain than specimen A0 no matter the present of an undercut. All specimens despite A0 and A4 fail in the undercut while those two have typical sheet metal failure.

Fig. 8. Stress-strain curve large-scale tests a) $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ b) room temperature

Printing the maximum force against the undercut depth as depicted in Fig. 9 a) there is a clear correlation between the depth and the reached force. This trend seems to be a bit bigger at lower temperatures (blue marks). It has to be marked that not always the deeper undercut leads to failure, in those cases the decisive undercut depth was chosen for Fig. 9 a). However, specimen A5, A7 and A8 appear to be below the average considering the undercut depth printed against the maximum force. This might be because after testing lack of fusion at the weld root got visible in those specimens. Nevertheless, considering the reduced area due to the undercut and compare it to the maximum force with respect to the maximum force of the reference specimen, the reduction in area is always higher than the reduction in strength as depicted in Fig. 9 b).

Fig. 9. Macrosection specimen A8

4 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

This study investigated the influence of undercuts on the load-bearing capacity of butt-welded joints. Undercuts are a type of weld imperfection that can reduce the strength of a weld joint by weakening the cross-sectional area. First an overview of the current regulation in standards is given. Afterwards, the experimental program and the manufacturing details for the butt-welded joints are presented. Later on, geometric and material properties of all specimens are summarized before the test results are discussed.

The study found that undercuts can have a significant impact on the strength of a welded joint. However, specimen A4 has an undercut depth which, considering the quality level limits of EN ISO 5817 (2), cannot be accepted. Even though, failure did not even occur in the undercut but in the sheet approximately 150 mm away from the welded area and no reduction in the load-bearing capacity became visible. Similar results have to be taken into account considering specimen A1. Despite the fact that failure occurred in one undercut, the failure strain is higher compared to specimen A0 and no reduction in the load-bearing capacity can be observed. In contrast, specimen A7 has a similar undercut depth compared to specimen A1 and A4 but the fracture strain and load-bearing capacity are clearly reduced. It should be noted that a variety of test specimens (A5, A7 and A8) were found to have lack of fusion in the weld root which seems to influence the performance of the welded joints. Some specimens with undercuts failed in the sheet metal, while others failed in the undercut.

This suggests that the severity of the undercut and the overall quality of the weld joint are both important factors in determining the load-bearing capacity of the joint.

In summary:

- The load-bearing capacity is highly influenced by the undercut depth.
- Up to an undercut depth of around 1 mm, the load-bearing capacity does not seem to be influenced in specific cases.
- For deep undercuts with $h > 1$ mm, failure always occurs in the undercut, while fracture strain and load-bearing capacity are significantly reduced. However, the limit could also be influenced by the sheet thickness.

Comparing the presented results to the limits postulated in EN ISO 5817 (2), for the undercut depth the load-bearing capacity and fracture strain seem not to be negatively influenced for some joint which would not fulfil the limit of the standard. It is also questionable whether quality level B and C should both be limited to the same absolute value, especially considering the execution rules of EN ISO 1090-2 (4). But it has to be noticed that the sheet thickness is not yet investigated in this study and should be considered in the future.

Nevertheless, to further investigate the influence of undercuts on the load-bearing capacity of butt-welded joints and develop more comprehensive understanding, future research should focus on the following aspects:

- Undercuts in various steel grades and filler materials: Exploring the behavior of undercuts in different types of steel, such as high-strength steels or low-alloy steels, as well as various filler materials and different combinations of base material and filler material strength (overmatching, matching, undermatching)
- Undercuts in different weld geometries: Investigating the influence of undercuts on the load-bearing capacity of fillet welds and T-joints, and considering the effect of the undercut geometry, such as undercut depth, width, and radius.
- Undercuts at extreme temperatures: Expanding the study to include even lower temperatures, such as -60 °C or -100 °C.

By conducting comprehensive research in these areas, we can gain a deeper understanding of the complex behavior of undercuts under various conditions, leading to the development of improved design, construction, and inspection practices for ensuring the safety and reliability of welded structures.

Further investigations on the influence of weld imperfections on the static load-bearing capacity are presented in (13). Studies on the fatigue strength of welded joints with imperfections can be found in (14–17).

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